

Research Article

Relationship Between Human Resource Management Strategy Practice and Worker Performance

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A B S T R A C T

Introduction: Various human resource management strategies (HRMS) have been implemented in industries nowadays to enhance the performance of employees. The study aims to examine the impact of HRMS on employee performance, in addition to finding the relationship between HRMS practice and worker performance. **Method:** To achieve the objectives of the study, a descriptive-analytical approach was used, where the study tool was a questionnaire. Thirty-four questionnaires were distributed to the people involved in building construction in Tilottama Municipality for the collection of the data. Relative Importance Index (RII) and mean were used to analyse the data. **Results:** From the research, among the surveyed HRMS, in building construction, the distribution of compensation and benefits was found to have the most impact on the performance of the employees. After that, the progress of the company depends on the type of leaders and their leadership styles. The security of the workers on the job was not mostly preferred in terms of the most impactful HRMS in building construction as it was ranked third. The impact of the distribution of wages on time was ranked fourth among the five surveyed HRMS. At last among all the surveyed strategies gender discrimination was ranked last to all the strategies. **Conclusion:** These strategies help to influence the performance of the employer. The strategies help to increase the performance of the employer to a certain level. From the calculation, the result showed that providing compensation and benefits helps to increase the working performance of the employees. The relative Importance Index of the surveyed strategies showed that compensation and benefits are ranked a the higher RII index value of 0.79. Leadership style and security were ranked second before timely wage distribution by the company.

Keywords: Strategy, PRACTICE, Human Resources, Construction, Leadership Styles, Relationship

Introduction

The construction industry of Nepal needs its human resources to perform.¹ The overall goal of performance management is to create a culture of high performance in which individuals and teams take responsibility for the continuous improvement of business processes and their skills and contribute to the achievement of goals set by managers.²⁻⁴ Management performance can be expressed mainly as the approximation of the individual goals of the workers to the organisational goals, provided that the workers support the company's culture. It states that expectations are to be defined and agreed upon in terms of roles and responsibilities. Also, worker performance is the most important of job performance; as it relates to completing tasks and achieving building goals; ensuring growth and sustainability. However, increasing employee performance requires attention to human resources as one of the pillars of success and creativity.⁵⁻⁷

Statement of Problems

HRM performs various tasks to improve workers' performance. The strategies used to improve workers' performance have been deferred. In a related context, many studies have shown that HRMS practice promotes the worker's performance in all fields of work. However, most of the studies didn't care about the construction industry. A study conducted by Bhatta et al. in 2018 showed that civil engineers working in construction companies in Nepal were generally satisfied with their jobs with an average job satisfaction score of 3.54, although they were not satisfied with the salary system and promotion opportunities. Contractors do not provide medical facilities on-site for casual workers. They are set up in such a way that they function without proper sanitary facilities, safe drinking water, proper food service, and others. Staff believes that there is a lack of medical facilities in the locality.⁸

Mishra et al. also highlighted these problems in the construction of Nepalese infrastructure projects.⁹ Good performance in any construction project means defect-free, the right things at the right time, and continuous improvement of the project. A study conducted by Maskey and Mishra in 2018 showed that the time spent by skilled and unskilled workers in productive work was 56.92% and 55.74% respectively.¹⁰ It means that the rest of their time is still unused. Therefore, it needs to effectively manage all levels of the work environment for the high performance of this industry. Mishra and Rai also compared different types of buildings and found that the performance for which people management is the most important should improve.¹¹

Objective

To explore the relationship between HRMS and worker performance in building construction

Methodology

Study Area

This descriptive study was conducted from December 2023 to March 2024. This research was conducted to identify the impact of HRM strategies on worker performance by Nepalese contractors in building construction. This study area covers those contractors who are involved in building construction projects in Tilottama Municipality, Nepal (Figure 1).

The GPS coordinates of Tilottama Municipality are 27.6193° N and 83.4750° E. The study area of this research was focused on Tilottama Municipality of Nepal (Figure 2).

Study Population, Sample Selection, and Sample Size

There are a total of 58 registered construction companies in Tilottama Municipality. These companies constituted the study population.

Out of 58 registered companies, 32 were selected as sample organisations to study the impact of HRMS on worker performance. The purposive sampling method is taken into consideration. Quantitative and qualitative data are taken from the sample population.

Nature of Data

Both primary and secondary data were required for the report. Primary data was collected through field visits, questionnaire surveys, Key Informant Interviews (KII), and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), where participants were consultants, contractors, and supervisors. Secondary data was collected from journals, books, etc.

- **Primary Data**

Primary data are those data that were collected directly in the field using various tools like field observation and questionnaire surveys in the field.

Field visits were organised to each construction company and their accessible projects to find out the best HRM practices implemented by the company in building projects.

The questionnaire survey was discussed with the representatives and the related documents were prepared.

Figure 1.A Map of Nepal

Figure 2.Tilottama Municipality Map According to Ward

- **Secondary Data**

Secondary data was collected from HRM-related books, journals, articles, papers, and thesis reports.

Methods of Data Collection

Data collection is the process of gathering and evaluating information or data from multiple sources in order to find answers to research problems, answer questions, evaluate results, and predict trends and probabilities. It is a crucial stage in all types of research and analysis.

During data collection, researchers must identify data types, data sources, and what methods are used. In this research, different methods were used for data collection. The methods used for primary data collection in this research were Questionnaire Survey, Key Informant Interview, and Focus Group Discussion.

- **Questionnaire Survey**

A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other challenges to collect information from respondents. A questionnaire can measure both qualitative and quantitative data, but it is more suitable for quantitative data collection. It is a good tool to protect the privacy of participants. The validity of data and information depends on the honesty of the respondent.

A list of questionnaires was prepared and an interview was conducted with the consultant, contractor, and worker of the construction company about HRMS and worker performance at the construction site. The questionnaire has been developed based on the works of Deshpande and Golhar, Forde et al., Grossman and Salas, Hassan, Huselid, Loosemore et al., Madhurima and Anjana, and McGrath-Champ and Rosewarne.¹²⁻¹⁹ The discussion was helpful in presenting each and every personal personality so that they could answer in their own way and the discussion shows that many of the construction companies are trying to utilise HR effectively to get the desired outcome.

- **Key Informant Interview**

Key Informant Interviews (KII) are qualitative research methods used to gather in-depth information from knowledgeable individuals within an organisation or industry. These individuals, known as key informants, have expertise and experience related to the research topic, making them valuable sources of information.

Below are two common techniques used to conduct key informant interviews:

- Telephone interviews
- Personal interviews

Out of the total sample, two experienced contractors and an engineer were selected for KII and were interviewed about the objectives of the research.

Focus Group Discussion (FGD)

Discussion groups were organised to find new things beyond a structured questionnaire or interview. The target participants in the focus group discussion were key stakeholders such as the consultant, the construction company's owner/ managing director, and various supervisors. Three discussion groups took place at the construction site.

Out of this, three discussion groups were conducted with contractor workers, workers, and consultants with an agenda on the management of human resources and its practices in the construction of building projects in Tiltotama Municipality and the impact of HRMS in the performance of the worker in the building construction. The discussion showed that maximum efforts were made to achieve the high performance of the workers in the building construction.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Data Analysis

The analysis of the data in this research began with summarising the data collected. Microsoft Excel was used for the data analysis and the results were represented with the help of pie charts, graphs, tables, etc. The analysis of these data was done by a method named Relative Importance Index (RII) method and from the calculation of the mean. RII was employed in analysing the retrieved data from the study's respondents as it assisted in the impact of HRMS in building projects.²⁰

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{AN}$$

Where, W: weights given to each factor by the respondents and ranges from 1 to 5, where 1 is very low and 5 is very high.

A: the highest weight (i.e. 5 in this study)

N: the total number of respondents

The RII was used to rank the different strategies' impact. These rankings made it possible to cross-compare the relative importance of the strategies. RII of each cause perceived by all respondents was used to assess the general and overall rankings in order to give an overall picture of the impact of HRM strategies on worker performance in Building projects of Tilottama Municipality of Nepal.

Data Presentation

The data collected from the questionnaire survey were analysed using Microsoft Excel Software. Data were analysed, interpreted, and presented using simple descriptive statistics, tables, bar charts, and pie charts.

Results and Discussion

Impact on Worker Performance with Timely Wages and Increase in Salary

The survey regarding the payment done by the company was done. The overall payment system of all of the companies seems to be good enough as the impact on worker performance due to an increase in salary does not seem to be 100% positive. As shown in Figure 3, out of 32

respondents, 18 i.e. 56.25%, replied that there is a positive impact on the employer after the increase in salary whereas 12 of them i.e. 37.5% felt there were no changes in the employer's performance after the increase in salary.

Figure 4 shows the impact of timely wages on worker performance. 18 of 32 respondents felt that there was an increase in the performance of the workers with the timely payment of the salary but 13 of them felt that there were no changes in the worker behaviour.

Mishra et al. said that the timely payment of wages boosts the confidence level of the worker.²⁰ Also, the management can create a positive image of the company among the employees with the proper distribution of wages on time. Worker increases their performance by about 10% from the previous regular time and also the responsibility of the worker would be increased with the increase in salary. Only 2 i.e. 6.25% of the respondents feel that the increase in salary is not only a factor in to increase in worker performance. Maskey and Mishra, Mishra et al., and Lama et al. addressed that sometimes the expectations of the worker won't be met by the company. They found that rather than an increase in salary worker performance is increased with the indication of the target and the commissions after the fulfilment of the target.^{10,21,22}

Figure 3. Impact on Worker Performance After an Increase in Salary

Figure 4. Impact of Timely Wages Distribution on Worker Performance

Impact of Recruiting Female Manpower at the Leading Position on Worker Performance

The building construction industry is one of the industries where the physical fitness of the worker is much needed in the field. Female manpower at the leading position in the construction business is favourable at the official level rather than the field level. Among the respondents, 15 of them i.e. 46.875% of the respondent felt that after the inclusion of the women manpower at the leading position the productivity of the worker increased, and 9

of them i.e. 28.125% of the total respondents felt that there were no changes in the worker performance from the later one after the appointment of the female leader in the building construction and 8 of them i.e. 25% felt that there was the negative impact of the female leader appointment in the building construction as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Impact on Worker Performance after the Appointment of a Female Worker in the Leading Position

Impact on Worker Performance with Job Security from the Employer

Job security was labelled in terms of various aspects such as contract agreement, supply of safety tools at the construction site, Insurance of the employees, on-field accidental compensation to the workers, and supply of new technologies in the construction. Every respondent reported that the performance of the workers increased drastically with the inclusion of various security aspects in the field. Security adjustment boosts their confidence to complete the job.

Safety is the most important factor governing the mentality of the worker to complete the work. Insurance of the employer, supply of safety tools, and on-site

accidental compensation seem compulsory in building construction as there is a high risk for the workers to do the work.²⁵ There may be height work, machinery work, and many other physical works that are very risky to be done. Falling of construction materials from the height may cause some accidents at the site. Out of the 32 respondents, 25 i.e. 78.125%, felt that the security of the worker highly recommended to increase the productivity of the employers, 7 i.e. 21.88%, felt no changes with any security addition to the employer as shown and none of them felt the degradation in the performance after the security provision in the building construction in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Impact on Worker Performance with Job Security from Employer

Impact on Worker Performance by the Addition of Compensation and Benefit by the Company to the Employer

Twenty-five respondents felt that there was a positive result in the employee after the addition of compensation and benefits in their working styles, 4 of them felt that the addition of compensation and benefits wouldn't be sufficient to increase the productivity of the employer and 2 of them got the negative result after the addition of additional payment system to the employer as shown in Figure 7.

Due to the different satisfaction levels of different employees, the demand for additional payments is also different. Thus, it did not only result in positivity in the employer behaviour rather negative behaviour also resulted.

Ghimire et al. discussed that the company goes through the performance of the workers and sometimes to keep the worker's willpower high at a certain point, the employees are awarded additional money or other certificates.²⁵ It somehow helps to boost the employer's productivity. Mishra and Aithal opined that

while distributing the awards, proper calculation of the effort of the employer must be done.²⁶ Neither may be positive for someone and may lead to negativity for the other one. Proper classification of the work must be done to get a positive result from the addition of compensation to the workers. Employer classification must done with the work distribution and the worker position and responsibilities. If it is not done in a wise way, it may result in much negative behaviour from the employees. Mishra and Aithal said sometimes the

company provides instant bonuses to the employees to boost their personal performance.²⁷ Bhatta et al. said that compensation and benefits to the workers were awarded as per the target given to the employees.⁸ Mishra and Aithal discuss that some of the employees felt a bias by the company in providing compensation to the employees which resulted in the development of negativity among the employees and the depletion of worker performance rather than an increase in the productivity of the workers.²⁷

Figure 7. Impact on Worker Performance by the Addition of Compensation and Benefit by the Company to the Employer

Impact on Worker Performance After a Change in Leadership Style by the Company

A leader is the one who directs the company. Good leadership will undoubtedly progress the company's economic as well as cultural aspects. There were various leadership styles accompanied by the construction company in building construction. All of the companies were satisfied with the leadership styles they were using in the present condition. Democratic leadership style was mostly used leadership style in building construction. 65.62% of the total respondents were satisfied with the performance of the worker after they changed the leadership style from the current style of leadership but only 18.75% of the total respondents felt that the change in leadership style from the previous used one was not enough to get the worker performance to increase rather

they got the depletion in the job so they returned to their original leadership style for building construction as shown in Figure 8.

Mishra and Aithal discussed that not only the leadership style, but the appointment of the leader by the management also hamper employee performance. Each one in the leading position must have a good nature for the proper completion of the building project. A good leader may induce employee behaviour and get positive results from them. If the appointment of the leader is not appropriate with the nature of the work, however the higher the experience and education, he/ she won't be able to get the job done wisely. So during the appointment of the leader for a building project, management must take care of this whole thing.²⁷

Relationship Between HRMS and Worker Performance

The relationship between HRMS and Worker Performance (WP) is done from the calculation of mean and RII of the performance of the workers with the application of the strategies in the daily routine of the employees. The higher the value of the mean higher the impact of that strategy on the worker performance. Figure 9 shows that the mean value of strategies timely wages, gender discrimination, security adjustment, compensation and benefit, and leadership style have a

mean of 3.41, 3.31, 3.66, 3.84, and 3.68 respectively. This shows that compensation and benefits have a maximum mean value of 3.84 and gender discrimination has a minimum mean value of 3.31. This shows the impact of the various HRMS on worker performance. These various HRMS relate differently to the worker's performance. The higher the mean value, the higher the impact, and the lower the mean value, the less the impact on the worker performance.

Figure 9. Comparison of Mean Values for Various Human Resource Management Strategies

Similarly, the relationship between HRMS and worker performance was matched by the calculation of RII for the strategies and their effectiveness for worker performance. RII for HRMS timely wages, gender discrimination, security adjustment, compensation and benefit, and leadership style has the RII values of 0.70, 0.68, 0.75, 0.79, and 0.75, respectively as shown in

Figure 10. Accordingly, the RII of compensation and benefits has a higher value of 0.79 and gender discrimination has the lowest value of 0.68. With the values of RII, the impact of HRMS and worker performance can be ranked from the higher value of RII to the lowest value of RII.

Figure 10. Relative Importance Index Comparison for Various Human Resource Management Strategies

Conclusion

The survey showed that an increase in the salary of the employees has 56.25% positivity on a worker's performance. The survey showed that 46.875% of the total firms feel that women can also lead at the leading position in building construction. 78.125% feel that the job security of the employees increases their performance. The higher the job security assurance from the employer, the higher the output from the workers. Compensation and benefits to the workers from the employer according to the various variables increase the performance of the worker by 78.125%. Around 65.125 % of the firms are totally satisfied with the leadership styles accompanied by those firms. HRMS help to influence the performance of the employer. The strategies help to increase the performance of the employer to a certain level. The result showed that providing compensation and benefits helps to increase the working performance of the employees. The relative Importance Index of the surveyed strategies showed that compensation and benefits are ranked with a higher RII index value of 0.79. Leadership style and security were ranked second before timely wage distribution by the company. Gender discrimination was ranked as the last of the strategies that affect the performance of the worker. Human resources management strategies are factors that help achieve company goals and enhance the ability to maintain and develop their employees' output. It has become clear that these strategies are very important despite their weak implementation in the construction industry where compensation and benefit strategy was ranked first. Human resources management strategies enhance worker performance in the construction industry, which requires establishing a human resources management department. It is necessary for companies to develop their organisational structures which include a competent human resources department. The need to develop motivational systems and promotions is commensurate with the status, abilities, and qualifications of workers. All HRM functions relate to job performance and thus project and company success in achieving goals. Clear selection and recruitment policies should be developed that meet the needs of the project, which they describe as being objective. Attention should be paid to psychological factors related to job satisfaction, inclinations, and attitudes of workers towards construction work and programmes should be developed to support their tendencies and attitudes. Participation of workers in all administrative actions and decision-making processes should be encouraged. The article recommends various ways to increase the performance and productivity of workers, like training workers about the use and importance of safety tools used in construction, assigning

them tasks commensurate with the nature of their qualifications, and mental and physical abilities, paying attention to the ideas of creative workers and give them the freedom to express their opinions and ideas, etc.

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